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The COOL-Process – a holistic recycling approach for lithium recovery

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Dr. Sandra Pavón, Alexander Nickol, Dr. Sebastian Hippmann, Dr. Mareike Partsch, Prof. Dr. Alexander Michaelis

Strategy for a circular economy

Make recycling strategies work

- ✓ **True recycling**
 - Primary product quality
 - Specification conform materials
- ✓ **Planetary boundaries**
 - Zero-waste
 - Low carbon footprint
 - Energy and resource efficiency and use of renewable energies
- ✓ **Electrified processes**
 - Benefit:
 - Higher degree of automatization
 - Digitalization
- ✓ **Targeting the real needs of industry**

Development of high tech applications

Safeguarding the raw material basis

Key technologies & sectors

Critical Raw Materials for the EU (2023)

34 CRMs including Lithium, Manganese, Copper, Nickel, Cobalt, Graphite

Lithium

Raw material situation

- Lithium is considered one of the **essential metals** for future technologies
- Continuous **increase** in lithium **demand** in the coming years
- **Production** (82,000 t/year) and **Reserves** (21 mill. t) placed mainly in Argentina, Chile, Australia
- **Price** evolution:

- Li Li_2CO_3 price has more than doubled in a short time
- Li On the spot market, the price is >25.000 USD/t
- Li This increases the supply risk → **Critical Raw Material**
- Li This results in a need for action to secure the raw material base for domestic industry.

U.S. Geological Survey, Mineral Commodity 2021, **2021**

Trading Economics, "Lithium Carbonate," available at <https://tradingeconomics.com/commodity/lithium>, **2023**

European Commission, Critical Raw Materials Resilience: Charting a Path towards greater Security and Sustainability, Belgium, **2020**

* price by end Q1 2023

Lithium

Recycling

Primary Raw Materials

- Saline lithium deposits
 - Salt lakes: ~75% of world production
- Mineral lithium deposits

Secondary Raw Materials

- Lithium primary batteries
 - Lithium anode
- Lithium secondary batteries
 - Lithium ion batteries (LIBs)

Lithium Recycling

Status quo and alternative

Hydrometallurgical approaches

- Digestion with inorganic or organic acids
- Complex downstream processing
- Production **high amount waste water**
- Isolation of Li is last step
 - **High losses**
 - **Low purity**

Pyrometallurgical approaches

- High energy consumption
- High investment costs
- Potential hazardous gas emission
- Complex extraction process for metal recovery
- Li remains in slag

Lithium Recycling

Status quo and alternative

Hydrometallurgical approaches

- Digested with inorganic reagents
- Complexation and precipitation
- **High amount waste**
- Li is lost
- **Loss**

Biological

- High consumption
- High investment costs
- Potential hazard
- Complexation process for recovery
- Li remains in slay

COOL-Process

- Leaching with supercritical CO₂ (**sc-CO₂**)
- Advantages:
 - ✓ Low chemical cost
 - ✓ No complex wastewater treatment
 - ✓ High **selectivity** for Li

- **Holistic process**, which is able to recover lithium from primary and secondary sources

PATENTED

Lithium Recycling

COOL-Process

Holistic recycling of primary and secondary raw materials

Recycling optimisation in laboratory scale

COOL Process for **primary** resources – spodumene, zinnwaldite,...

- **Thermal pre-treatment of minerals:** $T \sim 900-1.100^\circ\text{C}$
 - Mineral phase transformation (β -spodumene)
- Leaching with **sc-CO₂**
- Si, Fe remain in the solid residue
- **Lithium recovery:**
 - Spodumene: **~ 79-82 wt. %**
 - Zinnwaldite: **~ 75 wt. %**
- **bg-Li₂CO₃** as a product (**> 99.5 wt. %**)

Sustainability and economic evaluation

COOL Process for **primary** resources – COOL vs. spodumene process (zinnwaldite)

Economic evaluation*

	COOL Process	Spodumene Process
CAPEX [US\$]	11 480 760	6 844 140
OPEX [US\$]	7 953 729	12 526 243

COOL Process:

- Less operational costs due to less chemicals and wastewater
- Higher invest costs for pressure reactor

* based on an annual operating time of 8.000 h and a production volume of 2.000 t lithium carbonate

Sustainability

Optimisation of recycling processes in **pilot scale**

Challenges for cost-effective operation

COOL Process in TRL 5 possible?

200L- Autoclave reactor

Electrodialysis

Crystallisation/
Precipitation

- Decreasing **L:S ratio** for higher throughput and less wastewater production

Input: 1 t zinnwaldite; Li-extraction 71% (Output: 38 kg Li_2CO_3)

	L:S = 30	L:S = 20	L:S = 10
Water [L]	30.000	20.000	10.000
Solid [kg]	1.000	1.000	1.000

- Connecting several reactors for quasi-continuous operation
 - Effective use of unconsumed CO_2
 - Reuse of mother liquor

About the project

To boost the green transition, the availability of CRM needs to be ensured. The battery sector has been experiencing increasing demand for raw materials for years and is vulnerable for supply risks. Various strategies are being pursued to meet the growing demand for critical raw materials and to build up viable, sustainable and innovative value chains. Waste valorization by recovery and recycling plays a central role.

Objectives

- Recover valuable materials from primary and secondary resources (tailings)
- Demonstrate sustainable production and recovery of critical battery metals
- Assess End-use of the recovered critical battery metals
- Identify and characterise the critical battery metals with innovative technologies
- Enable social participation, stakeholder engagement and networking

<https://metallico-project.eu/>

Five different processes for metal recovery from primary and secondary raw materials

- **COOL+**

Li recovery and **geopolymers** production

- **TAILCO**

Co recovery from tailings in Cu hydrometallurgical plants

- **PURGES**

Co recovery from purges generated in pyrometallurgical refining processes

- **CONI**

Co, Ni and Cu recovery from waste alloys (Fe-As) generated in Pb hydrometallurgical processes

- **COMAN**

Co, Cu and Mn recovery from tailings generated in ore concentration plants.

Duration: 4 Years

21 Partners

9 different countries

50% Companies

EU-Contribution:

€ 11 798 783,25 €

<https://metallico-project.eu/>

Recycling process validation

COOL+ Process

ZERO
WASTE

Lithium recovery from primary raw materials

Value chain

Partners involved

Recycling process validation

COOL+ Process

Necessary thermal treatment

- Increased ionic porosity due to a more open, zeolite like structure
- After thermal treatment milling and sieving steps
- Leaching with sulfuric acid, which has a high cost and environmental impact

- Quality of input material (spodumene-rich) required
 - Melting point depression from quartz or fluorides

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Thank you for your attention!

Dr. Eng. Sandra Pavón
Recycling & Green Battery
Tel. +49 3731 2033-169
Fax +49 36601 9301-3921

sandra.pavon.regana@ikts.fraunhofer.de

 METALLICO

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